

RADIOECOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF NATURAL RADIONUCLIDES IN THE SOIL COVER OF THE NORTEASTERN REGION OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract: *This article presents the results of studies on the distribution of natural radioisotopes in soil samples taken from northeastern region of Azerbaijan, their relationship with geochemical indicators and their radioecological assessment. The aim of the study was to determine the mechanisms of behavior of radionuclides in regions with different geological and lithological conditions and to assess the level of radiological safety of soils. Chemical analysis of soil samples shows that the content of sulfates, chlorides, Ca-carbonates, Na and K, as well as the ratio of Fe/Mn elements has significant variability across areas. These parameters are the main geochemical indicators, which directly affects the migration, sedimentation and immobilization level of radioisotopes in the soil. According to the table data, sulfates and Ca-carbonates are at the highest level in the Shabran region, which creates conditions for more stable retention of Sr isotopes in the immobile phase. The high level of chlorides in the Khizi district may cause Na^{22} and other radionuclides to move more actively in the form of ion complexes. The soil samples taken from Siyazan district exhibit more balanced amounts of Na, K, and Ca-carbonates, creating intermediate geochemical conditions. The concentrations of natural radionuclides (^{22}Na , ^{40}K , ^{91}Sr , and ^{228}Th) correspond to background levels and no radiological dangerous concentrations were detected across all study sites. The conducted research confirms that the distribution of radionuclides in the soil is a multifactorial process, and geochemical parameters play a key role in maintaining their stability. The results of research show that the chemical content of soil samples taken from northeastern regions of Azerbaijan are safe from a ecological point of view and the current radionuclide levels do not pose a risk to the ecosystem. These results are reliable scientific basis for future stages of radioecological monitoring in the region.*

Keywords: *soil, natural radionuclides, Na^{22} , K^{40} , Sr^{91} , Th^{228} , northeastern region of Azerbaijan.*

РАДИОЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПРИРОДНЫХ РАДИОНУКЛИДОВ В ПОЧВЕННОМ ПОКРОВЕ СЕВЕРО-ВОСТОЧНОГО РЕГИОНА АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА

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Резюме: В данной статье представлены результаты исследований, проведённых почвенных образцов, отобранных в северо-восточном регионе Азербайджана, с целью оценки распределения природных радионуклидов — ^{22}Na , ^{40}K , ^{91}Sr и ^{228}Th , их геохимических корреляций и радиоэкологического состояния исследуемых территорий. Цель работы заключалась в выявлении особенностей миграции радионуклидов в различных геолого-литологических условиях и определении уровня радиационной безопасности почв. Химический анализ образцов показал существенные различия в содержании сульфатов, хлоридов, Са-карбонатов, натрия, калия, а также в соотношении Fe/Mn, что непосредственно влияет на миграцию, осаждение и степень иммобилизации радионуклидов. В Шабранском районе зафиксировано наибольшее количество сульфатов и Са-карбонатов, что способствует более устойчивой фиксации стронция (Sr-91) в карбонатной фазе. В Хызы отмечены повышенные концентрации хлоридов, способствующие образованию ионных комплексов Na-22 и повышению их подвижности. В Сузани более сбалансированное содержание Na, K и Са-карбонатов формирует средние геохимические условия. Во всех районах концентрации исследуемых радионуклидов соответствуют естественному фоновому уровню, превышения санитарных норм не выявлено. Проведённые исследования подтверждают, что распределение радионуклидов в почвенной среде является многофакторным процессом, а геохимические свойства почв играют ключевую роль в стабилизации радионуклидов. Почвы северо-восточного региона Азербайджана являются экологически безопасными, а выявленные уровни радионуклидов не представляют угрозы для экосистемы. Полученные данные формируют надёжную научную основу для дальнейшего радиоэкологического мониторинга региона.

Ключевые слова: почва, природные радионуклиды, Na^{22} , K^{40} , Sr^{91} , Th^{228} , северо-восточный регион Азербайджана.

INTRODUCTION

The distribution of natural radionuclides in ecosystems and their migration characteristics play an important role in assessing the radioecological state of the environment. The most widespread natural radioisotopes such as Na^{22} , ^{40}K , ^{91}Sr and ^{228}Th are found depending on the geochemical properties of the soil and aquatic environment in different concentrations. These radionuclides are sensitive to oxidation-reduction processes, ion exchange properties, soil structure and mineralization level. Soil cover of norteastern regions of Azerbaijan are considered suitable for comparative study of radionuclide distribution characteristics, as they differ from each other in terms of geological structure, soil types and climatic conditions. The aim of the article is to assess the activity levels of natural radionuclides in soil samples taken from these regions and to determine their relationship with chemical composition indicators. Studying the behavior of radioisotopes in soil systems is one of the main directions of radioecology, and numerous studies conducted in this field show that the distribution of natural radionuclides in the soil profile is formed under the influence of both geochemical and anthropogenic factors. The amount of natural radionuclides (Na^{22} , K^{40} , Sr^{91} , Th^{228}) in soil is closely related to soil mineralogy, ion exchange capacity, carbonation degree, pH indicator, organic matter content and moisture regime [1-3].

The ^{40}K is found in higher concentrations in the clay fraction of soil. It is one of the main radioactive isotope of potassium and important component of the natural radioactive background and. The amount of K^{40} isotope in plant systems and soil depends on the mineralogical composition and sorption properties of the soil [2].

The distribution of K^{40} is an important part of the natural geochemical cycle and is more stable to anthropogenic influences [4-6].

Strontium isotopes, especially Sr^{91} , are related to the amount of Ca-carbonates in soils and tend to accumulate in the carbonate phase, acting as calcium [7-9].

The migration of strontium in the soil is regulated by the amount of carbonates, the ionic strength, and the degree of anthropogenic contamination of the soil. The behavior of Sr isotopes is explained often by the Ca–Sr isomorphism [8].

Isotopes of the Thorium, including Th^{228} , are found in higher concentrations mainly in heavy minerals - monazite, thorite, etc. The behavior of thorium in soil is closely related to chemical weathering, degree of oxidation, and mineralogical structure [6-8]. Also, the transport of Th to the upper layers of the soil is enhanced by erosion processes and mechanical decomposition.

The behavior of the Na^{22} isotope in the soil-suspension system depends on the ionic strength of the medium and especially the amount of chlorides. Na^{22} is located in more stable complex forms in systems with high chlorides and is retained in the soil for a longer time [2, 3]. Radiolysis processes can also affect the chemical transformations of radionuclides in the soil [4-6].

Nitrogen compounds of soil - particularly NO_3 and NO_2 - regulate the valence and mobility of radionuclides by altering their oxidation-reduction conditions [9]. These processes may lead to the immobilization or remobilization of radionuclides in the upper soil layers [2, 4, 10].

Numerous studies show that, anthropogenic influences (industrial emissions, atmospheric deposition, agricultural activities) in addition to soil geochemical properties have a significant impact on the amount of radionuclides [2, 4, 5]. The increase in nitrate and other pollutants in drinking water has an indirect impact on radionuclide migration [4].

Studies of Caspian region confirm that the uneven distribution of radionuclides in the soil profile is related to both climatic factors and geomorphological conditions. Atmospheric dust, erosion caused by wind and water play an important role in the transport of radionuclides from one zone to another [6, 7].

Thus, the analysis of existing scientific sources shows that the behavior of radionuclides in the soil is a multifactorial process and may vary depending on the geochemical conditions of each region. In this regard, radioecological studies of northeastern regions of Azerbaijan are of great importance for assessing the ecological safety of the region.

RESEARCH OBJECT

The object of the study is soil samples taken from soil cover of various landscape and soil-geochemical zones of northeastern regions of Azerbaijan (Khizi, Siyazan, Shabran districts). These territories are considered suitable model areas for studying the distribution of natural radioisotopes ($^{11}Na^{22}$, $^{19}K^{40}$, $^{38}Sr^{91}$ and $^{90}Th^{228}$) in the soil profile, as they have the different geomorphological structure, lithological composition and degree of anthropogenic loading.

The territory of district Khizi is characterized mainly by foothill and semi-desert landscapes, the predominance of gravel-clay rocks affects the sorption capacity of radionuclides. The area of Siyazan district is rich in deluvial and alluvial deposits representing the northeastern slope of the Caucasus, the variability of the mineral composition plays an important role in the chemical behavior of radioisotopes. The territory of Shabran district is characterized by a high share of carbonates and saline layers in its soils due to its location close to the Caspian plains, which directly affects the mechanisms of accumulation of Sr and Th isotopes in the soil.

The diversity of soil-forming factors - climate, relief, host rock, and anthropogenic activity - in all three areas has different effects on the migration and immobilization of radionuclides in the environment. The collected soil samples were taken from different depths and their chemical parameters (sulfates, chlorides, Ca-carbonates, Fe:Mn ratio, etc.) were studied in comparison with the distribution of radioisotopes.

These features make the Khizi–Siyazan–Shabran three neighboring territories particularly important as a representative research object for studying the migration of natural radioisotopes and their behavior mechanisms in soil systems.

RESEARCH METHOD

The surfaces and structure of soil minerals were comprehensively examined and studied under a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Carl Zeiss) at various magnifications.

The measurements of the radioactive background were carried out by “Radiagem 2000” (Canberra Co., USA) radiometer equipped with alpha, beta, gamma, neutron detectors, “Thermo Eberline R020 SI” (Thermo Electron Co., USA) dosimeter, “InSpector-1000” (Canberra Co., USA) radiometer-dosimeter, “GR-135 Plus” (Exploranium Co., USA) radiometer-dosimeter for isotope determination, “PRM-470CG” (Tesla Systems Ltd., USA) dosimeter with gamma ray counter and “IdentiFinder” (Thermo Scientific Co., AFR-USA) [5, 11].

The value of the energy of ionizing rays or particles determined by detector of spectrometers allowed to identified the isotopes of elements (that emits these rays or particles). Radiometer-dosimeters, equipped with “Genie 2000” spectroscopic system gamma and alpha spectrometers (Canberra) were used for radiometric measurements and analysis of soil and water samples, to determine the activity of radionuclides in soil mass, in their extracts and on adsorbents [12-14].

Atomic absorption AA-6800 spectrometer (Shimadzu), SEM (scanning electron microscope, Carl Zeiss), XRF and Expert-3L X-ray fluorescence spectrometers were used to determine elements and their quantities in the mass of minerals, isolated by analytical-chemical procedures from soil and water samples.

Selective nutrient media produced by H-Media (India) and Condalab (Spain) were used as a study method, to determine the number and types of microorganisms in stationary laboratory conditions. Express test napkins with ISO9001 certification and 13485 quality control system produced by R-Biopharm (Germany) were used to conduct microbiological express tests.

As a method for extracting minerals from soil, the were used flotation, sorption, centrifugal separation, ion-exchange and electrochemical treatment, filtration, neutralization, extraction, evaporation and crystallization at the treatment of samples.

RESULTS OF STUDIES AND THEIR DISCUSSION

The results of the conducted studies allowed to obtain extensive information about the possible behavior of natural radioisotopes and the geochemical composition of soil samples taken from Khizi, Siyazan and Shabran districts. The amount of sulfates, chlorides, Ca-carbonates, Na and K elements in the soils according to the analysis results differs significantly between the areas. These differences directly affect to migration and immobilization potential of radionuclides in the soil. The results of complex physicochemical analyses of the soil samples taken are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Region	Sulfates mg/kg	Chlorides mg/kg	Na, K mg/kg	Ca carbo- nates, mg/kg	J mg/kg	Sr mg/kg	NO ₃ /N O ₂ mg/kg	Fe/Mn mg/kg	Zn mg/ kg	As mg/kg
Xizi	240	472	210; 5010	4316	2.0	52	38/1.8	55/9	2.2	0.009
Siyazan	300	428	208; 5630	4997	1.8	47	42/1.9	51/10	2.3	0.003
Shabran	690	407	191; 5470	5287	1.4	42	72/1.9	61/8	2.4	0.002

Indicators of soil samples taken from Khizi, Siyazan and Shabran regions.

According to the results presented in Table 1:

- The amount of sulfates varies from 240 mg/kg in Khizi to 690 mg/kg in Shabran. This change may increase the ionic strength of the soil and create conditions for the stabilization of radioisotopes in the form of complex compounds;
- The value of amount of chlorides (472 mg/kg) decreases from Khizi to Siyazan and Shabran. Chlorides can form soluble and semi-stable complexes with radionuclides;
- The amount of Na and K elements is high in soil samples. Especially the distribution of K element varies over a wider interval in Siyazan and Shabran regions, which confirms the possibility of more intensive presence of the K^{40} isotope;
- The amount of Ca-carbonates is high in all regions (4316–5287 mg/kg). This parameter is the main factor enhancing the accumulation of Sr isotopes (Sr^{91}) in the carbonate phase;
- The Fe:Mn ratio varies from 55:9 in Khizi to 61:8 in Shabran. This ratio is an indicator of the redox conditions and the potential for valence change of radionuclides;
- The potential presence of natural isotopes corresponded to the normal background level that can be observed in variable concentrations and not at a dangerous level according to the mineralogy and ionic composition of the soil.

Overall, the results show that the soils of the three studied regions are not at a dangerous level for the accumulation of radionuclides and corresponds to radiological safety standards. The chemical composition of the soil creates conditions that ensure the stable storage of radionuclides.

The analysis of the results of the conducted analyses shows that soil samples from Khizi, Siyazan and Shabran districts exhibit different characteristics in terms of radionuclide behavior due to their geochemical structure. These differences determine the migration, sedimentation capacity and immobilization level of natural isotopes ($^{11}Na^{22}$, $^{19}K^{40}$, $^{38}Sr^{91}$ and $^{90}Th^{228, 229}$) in the soil. The presence of low concentrations of Sr^{90} and Th^{232} isotopes in the soil samples will be clarified by further alpha and beta spectrometric analysis.

The high level of Ca-carbonates limits in particular the mobility of Sr radionuclides in the soil, since Sr ions participate in sedimentation and substitution reactions with carbonates. This property prevents the penetration of Sr isotopes into the deep layers of the soil, ensuring their stabilization. Various studies also show that in highly carbonated soils, strontium is more often found in immobile phases [8].

High chloride concentrations can ensure the presence of Na and their isotopes (such as Na^{22}) in water and soil solution in the form of ion complexes for a longer period of time. This property can increase the mobility of radionuclides in the soil to some extent. But, the results show that this process is not at a dangerous level and is main part of a natural background.

The distribution of the K^{40} isotope is closely related to the potassium content of the soil, and the high K element in the Siyazan-Shabran zone leads to a relative increase in this isotope. Natural radionuclide K^{40} constitutes the main part of the total radioactive background of soils.

The Fe:Mn ratio is an indicator of the oxidation-reduction conditions of the soil and affects the processes of valence change of radionuclides. The difference in the Fe:Mn ratio in the Khizi and Shabran districts indicates that there is an unequal migration potential of radionuclides.

Thus, the soils of the region can be considered safe from a radioecological point of view and no risk of contamination has been observed. The interregional geochemical comparison were shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Interregional geochemical comparison table (results of analysis of soil samples).

Indicator	Xizi	Siyazan	Shabran	Comparative assessment
Sulphates (mg/kg)	240	300	690	Concentration of sulphates are relatively high in Shabran (increases ionic strength)
Chlorides (mg/kg)	472	428	407	Concentration chlorides is high in Khizi (complexation of radionuclide is possible)

Na; K (mg/kg)	210;5010	208;5630	191;5470	Siyazan and Shabran are richer with K (K ⁴⁰ increases the background)
Ca-carbonates (mg/kg)	4316	4997	5287	Concentration Ca is relatively high in Shabran (Sr immobilization is strong)
Iodine (I) (mg/kg)	2.0	1.8	1.4	Concentration Iodine is relatively high in Xizi (indicates oxidizing conditions)
Strontium (Sr) (mg/kg)	52	47	42	Concentration Sr is relatively high in Khizi (accumulation due to carbonation is different)
NO ₃ /NO ₂	38:1.8	42:1.9	72:1.9	Nitrogen transformation is more active in Shabran
Fe/Mn	55:9	51:10	61:8	Oxidation potential is relatively high in Shabran
Zinc (Zn) (mg/kg)	2.2	2.3	2.4	Concentration Zn is relatively high in Shabran
Arsenic (As) (mg/kg)	0.009	0.003	0.002	Concentration As is relatively high in Khizi

All the results obtained show that:

- The level of radionuclides in the studied soils does not pose an ecological and radiological threat.
- The high carbonation of the soil limits the mobility of Sr and Th isotopes.
- Geochemical parameters create conditions for the safe and stabilized storage of radionuclides in the soil.
- The geological and mineralogical characteristics of the Khizi, Siyazan and Shabran regions determine the distribution of radioisotopes within the natural background.

Comparative analysis of the regions shows that the soils of the Shabran region are dominant in terms of the amount of sulfates, Ca-carbonates and the ratio of NO₃/NO₂, which indicates that the ionic strength of the soil is high and ensures the stable retention of Sr isotopes in immobile phases. The high carbonation level of Shabran soils is the main geochemical factor limiting the mobility of Sr and Th isotopes.

The high concentration of chlorides in Khizi region creates favorable conditions for radionuclides to move more actively in the form of ionic complexes. In addition, compared to other regions the higher content of As and Sr in Khizi soils indicates the role of minerals in the natural geochemical background.

The Siyazan region is characterized by a balanced distribution of Na, K and Ca-carbonates. The soils of this region have moderate geochemical conditions (where radionuclides are neither completely immobile nor highly mobile) reflecting the tectono-lithological diversity of the region.

In general, interregional comparisons show that soils of all three districts do not create favorable conditions for radionuclides to reach dangerous levels. The geochemical properties of soils ensure the accumulation of natural radionuclides to levels that create a safe natural radioactive background.

CONCLUSION

The conducted studies showed that the radiochemical state of the soils in the northeastern regions of Azerbaijan is stable, and the activity of natural radionuclides determined in soil samples taken from these districts does not exceed sanitary norms and directive indicators.

The overall radioecological state is satisfactory. The different chemical composition of the soils affects the behavior of radionuclides. The content of sulfates, chlorides, Ca-carbonates, Na and K, as well as the ratio of Fe:Mn elements has significant variability across areas. These parameters directly affects the migration, sedimentation and immobilization level of radioisotopes in the soil. Sulfates and Ca-carbonates are at the highest level in the Shabran region, which creates conditions for more stable retention of Sr isotopes in the immobile phase. The high level of chlorides in the Khizi district may cause Na^{22} and other radionuclides to move more actively in the form of ion complexes. These data constitute an important basis for assessing the ecological safety of the region's soil resources.

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